

Water quality in the Armutlu Beach

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Manuscript received online 20 October 2020, revised and accepted 31 October 2020

There is an ongoing relationship in terms of fishing, tourism and transportation both socially and economically on the coasts. It is important to investigate the dynamics of the coasts in terms of people who use them as recreation areas and aquatic creatures that use them as living spaces. For this purpose, the water quality was examined by measuring the sea water temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, salinity, and concentrations of As, Cd, Cu, Pb, Ni, and Zn daily between 5–14 August 2020 in Armutlu, Yalova. The levels of parameters were close to the previous studies. The order of heavy metal concentrations was: As > Pb > Zn > Cu > Ni > Cd. Armutlu coastline should be saved from pollution, destruction, and crass development.

Keywords: Sea water, water quality, heavy metals.

Introduction

Coastline have particular needs and stand in particular danger in crowded and fast developing Yalova city. Armutlu Beach is characterized by sandy and stony substrate¹ is located in the east of the Marmara Sea and is famous for water skiing, free diving, scuba diving, swimming and fishing activities. Besides having thermal springs, Armutlu also has rivers as Kaledere, Armutlu, Yamandere, and Uzundere so rivers can pollute the sea water if they are polluted. Due to the started services of Istanbul sea buses, fishing port, marina and fisher shelter in Armutlu, apart from those who earn their income with olive trees, the number of people working in tourism or port works has increased.

292 marine accidents have occurred in the Marmara Sea in the last 50 years². In 1994, the Bosphorus of Istanbul was badly affected by the 20.000-ton oil spill from tanker, Nassia colliding with a dry cargo ship, Shipbroker³. Similarly, the oil spilled into the sea from the explosion that occurred while repairing the DWT TPAO tanker in Tuzla Port in 1997³. In January 1999, 2,500 tons of fuel leaked from the “Marmara” tanker burning right around the coast of Armutlu provide habitats for cormorants, gray heron, ruddy shelduck, common pochard, duck, calico mallard, reed chicken, snipe, kingfisher, redfish, seagull, turbot, sole fish, oysters, mussels and sea snails².

Over 3000 marine species live in the sea of Marmara⁴, and in Erdek Bay, Bandirma, 988 individuals from 20 different exotic and rarest species were reported, including 10 actinopterygii, 6 crustaceans, 3 echinodermata, and 1 mollusc species⁵. Similarly, in 2015, sensitive (*Cystoseira barbata*, *Cymodocea nodosa*, calcareous red algae) and opportunistic algae (*Ulva* sp. and *Cladophora* sp.) were reported¹.

Temperature and dissolved oxygen concentrations is a prime factor in the production of ocean, carbon and nutrient cycles, and sea habitat⁶.

Pacific geoduck in the North American Pacific Coast is more positively affected by dissolved oxygen and negatively affected by average temperature rather than negatively affected by low pH in terms of protein abundance and shell growth⁷.

Just as increasing salinity may increase the peak as concentration, increasing dissolved oxygen also may increase the concentration of Pb, Cu, Cd released from the sediment in Daya Bay, South China Sea⁸.

Dissolved oxygen, pH decreased significantly between 1991 and 2015 in the Salish Sea and two NE Pacific estuaries, Washington, USA⁹.

pH and dissolved oxygen were significantly correlated

with trophic-functional groups as non-selectives, algivores, and bacterivores negatively and with predators positively in the Yellow Sea, China¹⁰.

The fishes cannot tolerate sudden changes in pH values¹¹, similar to the fish deaths in the study, in which there was a temperature value change of 4 degrees in February and 6 in July¹².

A significant dissolved oxygen difference was found between stations ($p < 0.05$) because of difference in photosynthesis, inhalation, water temperature, and salinity in Ildir Bay (Aegean Sea)¹³.

Principal component analysis showed that the sea of Marmara Sea is characterized by pH and dissolved oxygen in the 2014-2016 summer seasons¹⁴.

Experimental

In the Marmara University laboratory, the polyethylene bottles were kept in a mixture of 40% nitric acid and 60% deionized water for 24 h and rinsed 3 times with deionized water (ELGA purelab) and dried in the oven (Binder). The current study was carried out in Armutlu Beach, Yalova for 10 days. 10 sea water samples were collected and water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), pH, salinity (ppt), dissolved oxygen (mg L^{-1}) measured by using YSI ProQuatro multi parameter (Fig. 1) every day from 5 August to 14 August 2020. When one polyethylene bottle was filled with sea water, the sample were filtered through a $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ PTFE filter (Sartorius) with a sterile syringe and added 2% nitric acid (Merck) via micropipette and stored in the refrigerator until analysis began. The heavy metals in the seawater samples were identified using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-

Fig. 1. YSI ProQuatro multi parameter for measuring temperature, dissolved oxygen, salinity, and pH.

OES) (Spectro Blue) in seawater samples. The results obtained were analyzed by statistical package SPSS.

Results and discussion

Ayvalık Sea quality data is analyzed and descriptive statistics are explored. Four methods are used to investigate the normality assumption. Firstly, data distribution in the histograms is not exactly symmetric because they have not one prominent peak and equal tails to the left and the right. But detrended normal Quantile-Quantile (Q-Q) plot depicts the normal distribution of the sea quality values. Secondly, the coefficient variation (CV) which is the ratio of the standard deviation (σ) to the mean (μ) is greater than 30% for each quality parameter except Ni (Table 1). Thirdly, absolute values of measures of variability include the kurtosis and skew-

Table 1. Descriptive statistics analyze for Ayvalık Sea quality data

Parameter	σ	μ	CV	Skewness	Std. error	Kurtosis	Std. error	P
As	0.651	44.372	0.015	-0.493	0.687	-0.044	1.334	0.935
Cd	0.481	1.806	0.267	-0.833	0.687	-1.266	1.334	0.013
Cu	1.772	7.099	0.250	-0.590	0.752	-0.340	1.481	0.468
Pb	0.827	35.449	0.023	0.583	0.687	1.013	1.334	0.369
Ni	0.918	2.262	0.406	0.128	0.687	-1.355	1.334	0.346
Zn	0.813	12.676	0.064	1.076	0.687	-0.093	1.334	0.018
Temperature	0.599	24.140	0.025	0.482	0.687	0.367	1.334	0.833
DO	6.451	86.984	0.074	0.524	0.687	-1.514	1.334	0.085
pH	0.108	7.976	0.013	0.511	0.687	-0.382	1.334	0.593
Salinity (ppt)	0.535	25.830	0.021	-0.579	0.687	-0.484	1.334	0.456

ness are less than twice standard errors for each quality parameter and kurtosis and skewness values are between -1 and 1^{15} . Fourthly, significance value of the Shapiro-Wilk Test (P) for temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, salinity, As, Cu, Pb, and Ni data is greater than 0.05 (Table 1). Therefore, data distributions of all parameters are normal since they satisfy at least three of the 5 conditions.

The normal Quantile-Quantile plot for a sample of size 10 from a normally distributed values can be used for regression.

In August 2020, mean values for the sea water temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, salinity, and concentrations of As, Cd, Cu, Pb, Ni, and Zn are respectively 24.14°C , 7.98, 86.98%, 25.83 ppt, 44.37, 1.81, 7.10, 35.45, 2.26, and 12.68 ppb.

The strength of the relationship was classified with the Pearson correlation¹⁶. When amount of temperature increases, dissolved oxygen also increases because temperature has positive and strong association with dissolved oxygen (0.5 Pearson correlation). pH has a weak negative relationship with dissolved oxygen (-0.2 Pearson correlation), a medium positive relationship with temperature (0.3 Pearson correlation), but a medium negative relationship with salinity (-0.4 Pearson correlation). Salinity has a medium negative relationship with both dissolved oxygen and pH because the correlation values between salinity and dissolved oxygen and between salinity and pH are -0.3 and -0.4 respectively. As a result, salinity decreases when pH, and temperature increase.

The sea water temperatures, pH, and salinity were respectively from 23.2 to 25.3°C and from 7.82 to 8.16 and from 24.97 to 26.58 ppt, the dissolved oxygen was in the range of 80 to 96.46% . These dissolved oxygen values did not exceed the Turkish threshold values¹⁷ (in the range of 80 to 120%) as heavy metals did not exceed Turkish limit values¹⁸ (10 ppb for Cd, and Cu, and 100 ppb for As, Pb, Ni, and Zn). The pH values were in the range of the threshold values for Turkey¹⁸ ($6-9$) and EPA¹⁹ ($5-9$ for human health, and $6.5-8.5$ for aquatic life).

Concentrations of As (50 ppb), Cd (8 ppb), Cu (37 ppb), Pb (120 ppb), Zn (700 ppb) from polluted Dil Deresi stream water adversely affect to Izmit Bay, Marmara Sea²⁰ however our measured values were under threshold limits. Pb (less than 10 ppb) and Zn (21.75 ppb) in sea water samples from

Fig. 2. Temperature, dissolved oxygen, salinity, and pH predictions by regression.

Dil İskeleyi shore of Izmit²¹, mean of pH (8.59), temperature (21.8°C), dissolved oxygen (9.5 mg/L), and salinity (21.3 ppt) in Armutlu¹, and pH (between 7.8 and 8.5), and salinity (between 20.1 and 24.17) in Marmara Sea¹⁴ were close to our obtained values. The temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, and salinity were formulated by using regression and Fig. 2 shows that original values were predicted very closely by formulas (1–4).

$$T = 30.535 + 0.037\text{DO} - 0.538\text{SAL} + 0.535\text{pH} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{DO} = 10.497 + 0.244\text{SAL} - 10.842\text{pH} + 6.489\text{T} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{pH} = 9.329 - 0.069\text{SAL} + 0.031\text{T} - 0.004\text{DO} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{SAL} = 47.419 - 0.52\text{T} + 0.001\text{DO} - 1.149\text{Ph} \quad (4)$$

Conclusions

An explored descriptive statistic, which aimed to determine normality for Armutlu Sea quality data, was carried out during the period of 5–14 August 2020. This data was normally distributed. Moreover, the values of sea quality parameters did not exceed the limits for clean sea water. While salinity showed a negative linear relationship with the temperature, and pH, temperature showed a positive linear relationship with the dissolved oxygen. The formulas for temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, and salinity depending on each other were obtained via regression. When compared with the real values and the predicted values found by these formulas, it was seen that they were very close. Armutlu Beach may be monitored periodically for the prevention, re-

Kopuz: Water quality in the Armutlu Beach

duction and elimination of marine pollution, adaptation to the circular economy and climate change impacts, sustainable use and management of marine resources, urban, coastal and marine area planning with respect to the public health and marine life.

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